

The Impact of Green Marketing Mix on Green Loyalty in Outside Plant Based Milk Product with Green Satisfaction as Intervening Variable

Fayza Najeela Pakutandang¹, Indrawati²

^{1,2}Magister Management, School of Economics and Business, Telkom University, Bandung, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Currently, environmental conservation is a widely discussed topic as public awareness about its importance grows. Businesses need to recognize this trend, particularly by producing environmentally friendly products. Outside is one such popular eco-friendly brand that has gained significant traction within less than two years, competing effectively with long-established brands. Despite this success, Outside must continue to boost consumer loyalty through a strategic marketing mix approach to better understand consumer desires and prevent them from switching to other brands. This research aims to evaluate the impact of green marketing mix on consumers' green loyalty, with green satisfaction serving as an intervening variable. This understanding is essential for Outside to identify consumer needs and enhance loyalty in the competitive market. This research employs quantitative methods, incorporating multivariate techniques and descriptive analysis. The study sample consists of 300 consumers Outside in Indonesia. The data were analyzed using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) with the help of SmartPLS 3.0 software. According to the findings of this study, there is a significant and positive correlation between green products, green locations, and green promotions with green satisfaction and green loyalty indirectly. However, the variable of green pricing did not demonstrate a significant positive influence on green satisfaction or green loyalty indirectly. The research utilized a model with an R-square result of 0.254, indicating a moderate level of explanatory power. The study revealed a positive and significant impact of green products, green locations, and green promotions on green satisfaction and green loyalty indirectly. However, the variable of green pricing did not show a positive and significant influence on green satisfaction or green loyalty indirectly. The research employed a model with an R-square value of 0.254 or 25.4%, falling into the moderate category. Based on these findings, it is suggested that Outside offers more targeted promotions to its consumers, while ensuring profitability. This approach aims to enhance consumer satisfaction with Outside's environmentally friendly products, with the ultimate goal of increasing consumer green loyalty.

KEYWORDS: Green Marketing Mix, Green Satisfaction, Green Loyalty, PLS-SEM

1. INTRODUCTION

Plant-based milk products have become a trend in the food and beverage sector. Data from Rakuten Insight (2023) reveals that 86% of respondents aged 16 and over have consumed plant-based milk products like soy milk, almond milk, oat milk, and rice milk. The majority of consumers also agree that plant-based milk can be an alternative to cow's milk, as it provides all the nutrients with less fat and sugar (Food Navigator Asia, 2023). The growth projection for the milk substitute market continues to rise annually. According to Statista Market Insight (2023), the revenue for the milk substitute market in Indonesia reached US\$49.2 million in 2023, with an expected annual growth rate of 8.34% until 2028. One popular type of plant-based milk among consumers today is oat milk. This preference is due to the rapid increase in oat milk sales, making it a favorite milk substitute for both cafes and consumers (Saini, 2022). Additionally, oat milk has characteristics more similar to fresh cow's milk, such as a thicker texture, better frothing, and a creamier taste compared to other plant-based milk products, which often have a nuttier flavor that may be unfamiliar to regular cow's milk consumers. Furthermore, oat milk requires less land and water to produce, making it a more environmentally friendly option (Bangkok Post, 2022). According to data presented by Katadata Insight Center (KIC) in the "Katadata Consumer Survey on Sustainability," consumers decide to purchase environmentally friendly products for several reasons. These include a desire to contribute to preserving the Earth, satisfaction with the benefits provided, the positive image displayed by the brand of the environmentally friendly product, unintentional purchases, and lastly, because the brand of the product is highly favored by consumers (Katadata Insight Center, 2021).

These reasons align with the theory of green customer-based brand equity proposed by Chen (2010) and Kang & Hur (2011). The theory highlights consumer satisfaction with eco-friendly products (green satisfaction) and the preference and demand for eco-friendly

brands, which lead to continued purchases from these brands (green loyalty). However, consumers still face barriers when purchasing green products. According to data published by Databoks from an Ipsos survey in the e-Conomy Research report (2024), these barriers include a lack of information about green products, uneven availability of such products, and higher prices, as green products often incur additional production costs. These aspects correlate with elements of the green marketing mix described in the journal by Ubirajara et al. (2021): knowledge about green products falls under green promotion, the availability of green products relates to green place, and the pricing of green products pertains to green price. According to research by Kumar (2016), studies on green marketing will keep advancing and require broader discussions. This expansion aims to identify and categorize various targeting methods for green marketing strategies, emphasizing optimal options based on industry and company characteristics (Nguyen-Viet, 2022). Therefore, this research was conducted to address the gap in the field of green marketing.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Literature Review

1) *Green Marketing*

Green marketing involves a series of actions ensuring that every stage of the marketing process, from procurement to product delivery, is carried out with greater consideration for environmental sustainability (Mogaji et al., 2022). Green marketing takes into account the social and environmental impacts of marketing activities without compromising profitability (Mogaji et al., 2022). Green marketing involves efforts directed towards all consumers and integrates various aspects of marketing activities, such as price, planning, process, production, promotion, and people, with the aim of demonstrating the company's commitment to reducing the environmental impact of its products and services (Groening et al., 2018). Companies that develop products and services with environmental considerations generally aim to ensure long-term sustainability, explore opportunities in new markets, enhance sustainable profitability, and gain competitive advantage (Polonsky, 1994; cited in Troudi & Bouyoucef, 2020).

2) *Green Marketing Mix*

In general, green marketing mix strategies encompass the development of green products as well as pricing, promotion, and/or supply chain tactics specifically aimed at enhancing or maintaining environmental sustainability (Kinoti, 2011; cited in Davari & Strutton, 2014). These green marketing strategies can assist companies in enhancing their performance in long-term and sustainable profitability (Mukonza & Swarts, 2020). Green products refer to items with packaging that supports environmental conservation, can be recycled, reused, and biodegrade naturally. Additionally, green products are recognized for their minimal negative impact on the environment (Mukonza & Swarts, 2020). Green pricing strategies involve considerations of production and marketing costs, incorporating both economic and environmental aspects while still providing value to customers (Tripathi & Pandey, 2018). Green place analysis entails evaluating the entire distribution chain of green products, starting from the production stage to the product consumption stage (Ubirajara et al., 2021). Green promotional programs reflect communication strategies designed to provide stakeholders with information about a company's efforts, commitments, and achievements in environmental conservation (Dahlstrom, 2011; cited in Nguyen-viet, 2022).

3) *Green Satisfaction*

Customer satisfaction is an evolving perspective post-purchase, comparing customers' expectations of product and service quality anticipated from their experience with the actual quality of products and services received from the transaction (D. J. Kim, 2012). Green satisfaction is defined as the level of happiness associated with consumption experiences that meet consumers' desires regarding the environment, sustainable expectations, and needs supporting environmental sustainability (Chen, 2010; Gelderman et al., 2021; Nguyen-viet, 2022).

4) *Green Loyalty*

Loyalty is defined as a high level of commitment to continue purchasing or using a specific product or service in the future, even in the presence of situational influences or marketing efforts that could potentially shift consumer behavior (Kotler & Keller, 2016: 153). Green loyalty is defined as consumers' commitment to repurchase or continue using environmentally friendly brands, typically demonstrated through repeated purchases of eco-friendly products or services or other affirmative action such as word-of-mouth recommendations (Kang & Hur, 2011).

2.2. Hypothesis Development

1) *Relationship between green product and green satisfaction*

Companies that strategically engage with specific consumer groups using a consistent green marketing approach have the opportunity to create and produce eco-friendly products tailored to meet and satisfy the unique demands of environmentally conscious customers (Davari & Strutton, 2014). Therefore, the quality of green products is a crucial factor in the satisfaction of environmentally conscious customers (Gelderman et al., 2021). Consequently, high-quality green products can lead to greater green satisfaction (Nguyen-Viet, 2022). Based on the explanation of the theory above, the first hypothesis (H₁) in this research can be formulated as follows.

H₁: Green products have a positive and significant impact on green satisfaction

2) *Relationship between green price and green satisfaction*

Gelderman et al. (2021) explains that consumers with environmental knowledge are willing to pay higher prices for green products because they are satisfied with the benefits these products provide. Consequently, previous research has indicated a significant relationship between green pricing and green satisfaction (Gelderman et al., 2021; Nguyen-Viet, 2022). Based on the explanation of the theory above, the second hypothesis (H₂) in this research can be formulated as follows.

H₂: Green price has a positive and significant impact on green satisfaction

3) *Relationship between green place and green satisfaction*

According to Yoo et al., cited in Nguyen-Viet (2022), if a brand is easy to find anytime and anywhere, it can save consumers time and contribute to increased customer satisfaction. Green distribution or placement must ensure that the performance of green products on the market matches consumer claims and expectations to achieve satisfaction after purchasing green products (Agustini et al., 2019). Based on these points, several previous studies have indicated a significant relationship between green place and green satisfaction (Agustini et al., 2019; Nguyen-Viet, 2022). The third hypothesis in this research can be formulated as follows:

H₃: Green place has a positive and significant impact on green satisfaction

4) *Relationship between green promotion and green satisfaction*

Customer satisfaction can directly enhance management efficiency by strengthening the trust of existing customers, which in turn encourages repeat purchases, attracts new customers, and promotes a positive product image. These factors are crucial in motivating customers to make repeat purchases (W. H. Kim et al., 2019). Therefore, green promotion significantly influences green satisfaction (Nguyen-Viet, 2022). The fourth hypothesis in this research can be formulated as follows:

H₄: Green promotion has a positive and significant impact on green satisfaction

5) *Relationship between green satisfaction and green loyalty*

Customer satisfaction is a key goal pursued by businesses, as one of the long-term benefits of having satisfied customers is the creation of customer loyalty (El-Adly, 2019). Oliver, as cited in Gelderman et al. (2021), asserts that satisfied customers are significantly more likely to repurchase products or services compared to those who are dissatisfied or less satisfied. In the context of green businesses, Kang & Hur (2011) state that the positive perceptions consumers have towards eco-friendly products or services are likely to encourage repeat purchases and prompt them to recommend these products to others. The fifth hypothesis in this research can be formulated as follows:

H₅: Green satisfaction has a positive and significant impact on green loyalty

6) *Relationship between green marketing mix and green loyalty mediated with green satisfaction*

This study proposes several hypotheses to explain the indirect relationship between elements of the green marketing mix and green loyalty. Due to the limited research addressing this topic, these hypotheses represent a novel aspect of this study.

H₆: Green satisfaction will mediate the relationship between green products and green loyalty

H₇: Green satisfaction will mediate the relationship between green price and green loyalty

H₈: Green satisfaction will mediate the relationship between green place and green loyalty

H₉: Green satisfaction will mediate the relationship between green promotion and green loyalty

2.3. Theoretical Framework

Within this research framework, various concepts have been adopted from prior studies. For instance, to explore the relationship between elements of the green marketing mix (green product, green price, green place, green promotion) and green satisfaction, insights from research by Davari & Strutton (2014) and Nguyen-viet (2022) have been incorporated to enhance comprehension of

these components. Additionally, an innovative aspect of the analysis involves examining the indirect impact of the green marketing mix (green product, green price, green place, green promotion) on green loyalty, with green satisfaction serving as a mediator. Drawing from several previous studies with similar themes and after making necessary adjustments, a model has been developed, illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Measurement

In this study, several variables need to be measured, including green products, green prices, green places, green promotions, green satisfaction, and green loyalty. These variables will be assessed using a Likert Scale, which is defined as a scoring system that gauges the extent of a person's agreement or disagreement with statements made by the researcher. Additionally, the Likert Scale is used to evaluate respondents' reactions to the opinions presented in the questionnaire. Therefore, the Likert Scale was utilized in this research (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016: 210). The Likert Scale includes five response options ranging from 1 to 5, where 1 represents "strongly disagree," 2 represents "disagree," 3 represents "neutral," 4 represents "agree," and 5 represents "strongly agree." Since the information for this research was gathered via a questionnaire, the necessary steps to develop a good questionnaire include conducting a content validity test, an expert validity test, a readability test, and a pilot test. The author conducted a content validity test by using and modifying questionnaire items from previous studies published in reputable international journals (Indrawati & Putri, 2018).

3.2. Sampling and Data Collection

In this research, the sampling technique employed is non-probability sampling, meaning not all members of the population have an equal chance of being included in the sample (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016: 247). The specific type of sampling used is purposive sampling, where certain sample members are intentionally selected because they meet specific criteria and can provide the necessary information to address the research problem (Indrawati, 2015: 170). In this study, the criteria for respondents were Indonesian citizens aged 16-65 years (Ipsos, 2022; Rakuten Insight, 2023). Additionally, respondents needed to be consumers who had purchased and consumed Outside plant-based milk products at least three times (Aaker, 1991). In this study, a questionnaire was distributed online through Google Forms to 500 respondents who met the specified criteria. Secondary data collection was also conducted to perform a literature review by seeking information from various articles, previous journal studies, research methodology books, websites, and other reliable sources. A total of 561 questionnaires were distributed and completed by respondents, but only 500 met the criteria to proceed with the rest of the questionnaire due to inconsistencies in responses during the screening question section.

3.3. Data Analysis

In this research, descriptive analysis was employed to gather information about the elements of green marketing mix, which includes green product, green price, green place, and green promotion, as well as the variables of green satisfaction and green loyalty, based

on respondents' evaluations. Additionally, this research examines the causal relationship between each element of the green marketing mix and green loyalty, with green satisfaction as a mediator. To find out this, SEM PLS is applied as a statistical analysis tool that places more emphasis on efforts to predict or explain variations, and aims to carry out exploration (Indrawati, 2015: 198). The validity of SEM-PLS is employed to evaluate the research instruments using convergent validity and discriminant validity. Convergent validity is measured through methods such as the correlation coefficient between items, factor loading, and average variance extracted (AVE). Discriminant validity is established when two variables, which are theoretically considered unrelated, show no correlation in empirical measurement results (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016: 222). Structural model testing is the second stage in PLS analysis. This stage focuses on evaluating the interactions between different latent variables (Indrawati et al., 2017: 70). The bootstrapping process is used to obtain the t-value. Since this study includes intervening variables that indirectly influence the dependent variable through independent variables, it is essential to calculate the extent of the indirect impact of the intervening variables. In addition to evaluating the path coefficient, the percentage of variance explained, represented by R², is also assessed for latent variables that depend on the independent latent variable (Indrawati et al., 2017: 71). The resulting R² values of 0.67, 0.33, and 0.19 indicate that the model is "good," "moderate," and "weak," respectively.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Respondent Demographic

The summary results regarding the demographics of respondents in this study are that 32% of male respondents filled out this questionnaire, and 68% of other respondents were female. The age range of respondents was mostly between 16-25 years, namely 83.33%, which can be categorized as the younger generation. It can be concluded that most consumers of Outside oat milk are the younger generation. The most common educational backgrounds in this study were high school, namely 52.67% and bachelor's degrees, 39.67%. In terms of work, most of the respondents in this study were students at 55.67%, and the rest were divided into several types of work such as civil servants, entrepreneurs, housewives, doctors, teachers and retirees. Then the last element is the monthly income range, which can also be likened to pocket money for students. Most respondents chose a range between Rp. 1,000,000-Rp. 3,000,000 per month, with a percentage of 36.67%. The following is a table that explains the demographic results of the respondents of this study.

Table 1. Respondent Demographic

<i>Respondent Demographic</i>			
Gender	Male	96	32%
	Female	204	68%
Age (in years)	16-25	250	83.33%
	26-35	36	12%
	36-45	6	2%
	46-55	7	2.33%
	56-65	1	0.33%
Educational Background	Elementary School	0	0%
	Junior High School	1	0.33%
	Senior High School	158	52.67%
	Diploma	13	4.33%
	Bachelor Degree	119	39.67%
	Master Degree	9	3%
Occupation	Doctoral Degree	0	0%
	Civil Servant	12	4%
	Entrepreneur	17	5.67%
	Corporate Employee	67	22.33%
	Freelancer	21	7%
	Student	167	55.67%

	Housewife	6	2%
	Teacher/Lecturer	7	2.33%
	Doctor	2	0.67%
	Retired	1	0.33%
Income Range (in IDR/month)	< Rp. 1.000.000	76	25.33%
	Rp. 1.000.000 – Rp. 3.000.000	110	36.67%
	Rp. 3.000.001 – Rp. 6.000.000	65	21.67%
	Rp. 6.000.001 - Rp. 9.000.000	30	10%
	> Rp. 9.000.000	19	6.33%

4.2. Analysis of Structural Equation Model (SEM) Results

4.2.1. Assessment of Measurement Model

Testing the outer model, or assessing the measurement model, is necessary to determine the validity and reliability of the research questionnaire. This assessment is crucial for evaluating how well the items explain the latent variable (Indrawati, 2017: 69). The measurement model section includes two testing components: the validity test and the reliability test. Figure 2 displays the processed results of the measurement model using the SmartPLS application.

Figure 2. Measurement Model Result

In the validity test section, several indicators determine whether the questionnaire items used in this research meet the validity requirements. The first indicator is convergent validity, which assesses the accuracy of an item or group of items in measuring the intended variable (Indrawati et al., 2017: 69). In this study, all items have factor loading values greater than 0.7 except for item PRO4 and PRO5, it has an invalid result. So here author decided to not include those items to proceed to the next analysis phase. In addition to factor loading values, convergent validity can also be assessed using average variance extracted (AVE) values. For convergent validity requirements to be met, the AVE value of each variable must exceed 0.5 (Indrawati, 2015: 153). In this study, all constructs had AVE values greater than 0.5, categorizing them as valid. The next indicator is discriminant validity, which indicates that a measurement instrument meets the standards if the constructively predicted variables do not have a high correlation. Thus, the measurement results should demonstrate that these variables are not highly correlated (Indrawati, 2015: 153). The standard for evaluating discriminant validity is through cross-loading values. According to Liu and Li in Indrawati et al. (2017: 70), an indicator is considered valid if its correlation value with the related construct is higher than its correlation value with other constructs. In this study, the cross-loading value within the same construct is higher than between different constructs. Therefore, it can be

concluded that this research meets the criteria for discriminant validity, as proven by the Fornell-Lacker Criterion results table below.

Table 2. Fornell-Lacker Criterion

	<i>GLO</i>	<i>PLA</i>	<i>PRI</i>	<i>PRT</i>	<i>PRO</i>	<i>GSAT</i>
Green Loyalty	0.826					
Green Place	0.475	0.769				
Green Price	0.673	0.595	0.754			
Green Product	0.487	0.286	0.459	0.774		
Green Promotion	0.527	0.337	0.464	0.407	0.837	
Green Satisfaction	0.504	0.439	0.474	0.512	0.595	0.801

Furthermore, to assess whether the measurement instrument in this study meets the criteria for discriminant validity, the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) results can also be used. The HTMT ratio shows the maximum correlation value between each pair of related variables. To differentiate between the two variables, the ratio of correlated variables must not exceed 0.85 (Indrawati et al., 2022). The results of the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio in this study are meet the standard for discriminant validity proven in the table below.

Table 3. Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio

	<i>GLO</i>	<i>PLA</i>	<i>PRI</i>	<i>PRT</i>	<i>PRO</i>	<i>GSAT</i>
Green Loyalty						
Green Place	0.536					
Green Price	0.781	0.713				
Green Product	0.567	0.324	0.538			
Green Promotion	0.634	0.404	0.569	0.498		
Green Satisfaction	0.575	0.497	0.553	0.593	0.723	

The subsequent step involves analyzing the outcomes of the reliability test, indicated by the Cronbach's Alpha (CA) value or other alternatives like Composite Reliability (CR), both of which should be at least 0.7 or higher (Indrawati et al., 2017: 70). This test evaluates how much the indicator variable increases when the latent variable increases (Indrawati et al., 2017: 70). The following table displays the results of the Factor Loading value, AVE value, Cronbach's Alpha (CA), and Composite Reliability (CR).

Table 4. Results of the Factor Loading value, AVE value, Cronbach's Alpha (CA), and Composite Reliability (CR)

<i>Construct</i>	<i>Factor Loading</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Composite Reliability</i>	<i>AVE</i>
<i>Green Loyalty (GLO)</i>				
GLO1	0.728			
GLO2	0.830			
GLO3	0.845	0.883	0.915	0.683
GLO4	0.866			
GLO5	0.855			
<i>Green Satisfaction (GSAT)</i>				
GSAT1	0.790			
GSAT2	0.825	0.859	0.899	0.641
GSAT3	0.849			
GSAT4	0.816			

GSAT5	0.716			
<i>Green Place (PLA)</i>				
PLA1	0.852			
PLA2	0.807	0.828	0.878	0.591
PLA3	0.748			
PLA4	0.725			
PLA5	0.703			
<i>Green Price (PRI)</i>				
PRI1	0.823			
PRI2	0.721	0.811	0.868	0.568
PRI3	0.752			
PRI4	0.749			
PRI5	0.719			
<i>Green Promotion (PRO)</i>				
PRO1	0.880	0.785	0.875	0.7
PRO2	0.834			
PRO3	0.794			
<i>Green Product (PRT)</i>				
PRT1	0.749			
PRT2	0.805	0.833	0.882	0.598
PRT3	0.802			
PRT4	0.746			
PRT5	0.764			

4.2.2. Assessment of Structural Model

The aim of assessing this structural model is to investigate the correlation between latent variables (Indrawati et al., 2017: 70). This evaluation entails scrutinizing the path coefficient values to ascertain their significance and reviewing the t-values, which are obtained through the bootstrapping process (Indrawati et al., 2017: 70). Figure 3 below presents the outcomes of the structural model testing conducted using the SmartPLS application.

Figure 3. Structural Model

This study adopts a significance level of 0.05 and presents a calculated t-value of 1.65. If the calculated t-value for each correlation between variables exceeds 1.65, it indicates a positive and significant relationship between these variables. Table 5 illustrates that all elements of the green marketing mix have a positive and significant impact on green satisfaction, except for one element, green price. The t-statistic and p-value results for green price indicate a value smaller than 1.65 for the t-statistic and greater than 0.5 for the p-value. Therefore, it can be inferred from this research that green prices do not significantly and positively influence green satisfaction. Similarly, in terms of the indirect influence of green marketing mix elements on green loyalty, mediated by green satisfaction, the green price variable also does not exhibit a positive and significant influence on green loyalty. Based on the data provided in Table 5, the variable of green promotion exhibits the most significant influence both directly on green satisfaction and indirectly on green loyalty, with a path coefficient value of 0.395 for the direct relationship and 0.199 for the indirect relationship. Consequently, it can be inferred that there is a need for Outside to enhance its green promotion efforts, as this research indicates that the green promotion aspect holds the greatest sway in increasing green satisfaction and green loyalty.

Table 5. Result of Structural Model

Hypothesis	Path Diagram	Path Coefficient (β)	T-Statistic	P-Value	Result
H ₁	PRT→GSAT	0.272	4.708	0.000	Supported
H ₂	PRI→GSAT	0.047	0.791	0.214	Not supported
H ₃	PLA→GSAT	0.2	3.68	0.000	Supported
H ₄	PRO→GSAT	0.395	8.112	0.000	Supported
H ₅	GSAT→GLO	0.504	12.97	0.000	Supported
H ₆	PRT→GSAT→GLO	0.137	4.38	0.000	Supported
H ₇	PRI→GSAT→GLO	0.024	0.774	0.22	Not supported
H ₈	PLA→GSAT→GLO	0.101	3.492	0.000	Supported
H ₉	PRO→GSAT→GLO	0.199	6.806	0.000	Supported

In addition to examining the path coefficient and t-value, the assessment of the structural model also considers the percentage of variance explained, represented by the R² value. The R² value indicates the extent to which the dependent latent variable is influenced by the independent latent variable (Indrawati et al., 2017: 71). R² values of 0.67, 0.33, and 0.19 suggest that the model is "good," "moderate," and "weak," respectively. In this study, the R² value obtained for the green satisfaction variable was 0.485, indicating that 48.5% of the variance in the green satisfaction variable can be explained by the green product, green place, and green promotion variables. Referring to the theory mentioned earlier, the model used to explain the green satisfaction variable falls within the moderate category. Additionally, there is an R² value for the green loyalty variable, which is 0.254, implying that 25.4% of the variance in the green loyalty variable can be explained by the green product, green place, green promotion, and green satisfaction variables. Therefore, the model used to explain the green loyalty variable also falls within the moderate category. Based on the analysis of the research results discussed earlier, the theoretical framework aligned with these findings is as follows.

Figure 4. Theoretical Framework with Result

5. CONCLUSION

5.1. Practical Implication

According to the research results mentioned earlier, out of the four elements of the green marketing mix, three elements impact green satisfaction and, through green satisfaction, also influence green loyalty. Therefore, the practical recommendations for Outside are as follows.

1) Green Product

Outside should persist in innovating by developing products that are both environmentally friendly and of high quality, meeting consumer needs. Additionally, they should include certification or proof of meeting environmentally friendly standards on their oat milk packaging to make this information easily accessible to consumers. This approach is expected to enhance consumer satisfaction with Outside's environmentally friendly oat milk products, ultimately leading to greater customer loyalty.

2) Green Place

Outside should strengthen its collaboration with retailers selling its products, aiming to collectively contribute to environmental preservation. One approach is to launch a campaign encouraging consumers to bring their own shopping bags, offering rewards like discounts or free Outside products. This strategy is expected to enhance consumer satisfaction and boost loyalty.

3) Green Promotion

Outside should enhance its promotional programs, including buy one get one deals, flash sales, and product bundling, to attract customers and provide satisfaction through lower prices. Repeated promotions during specific times, like payday sales, are expected to help boost consumer loyalty.

4) Green Satisfaction

Outside should enhance its consistency to continually deliver quality products, as consumers are generally more satisfied when their purchases meet or exceed expectations. Additionally, Outside needs to provide clear information about the benefits of environmentally friendly products and how these products contribute to environmental preservation. This approach will make consumers feel more satisfied, knowing they are playing a part in protecting the environment by consuming Outside oat milk products.

5.2. Literature Implication

This research only evaluates how the green marketing mix which includes green product, green price, green place, and green promotion influences green satisfaction and green loyalty indirectly. Therefore, the author provides several suggestions that can be considered for further research as follow. Firstly, future researchers could explore similar variables but focus on companies in different industries that share a commitment to environmental preservation, such as the cosmetics, automotive, or fashion sectors. Secondly, researchers could enrich their studies by introducing moderating variables like gender, age, or other factors that might intensify the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Lastly, it's important to note that the findings of this study may not fully represent the preferences of customers from other countries or regions, given that it solely focused on consumers of Outside oat milk products in Indonesia. Thus, future research could expand its scope to encompass other countries or regions to achieve a more comprehensive understanding.

REFERENCES

- 1) Aaker, D. A. (1991). *Managing Brand Equity: Capitalizing on the Value of a Brand Name*. The Free Press.
- 2) Agustini, M. H., Athanasius, S. S., & Retnawati, B. B. (2019). Identification of green marketing strategies: Perspective of a developing country. *Innovative Marketing*, 15(4), 42–56. [https://doi.org/10.21511/im.15\(4\).2019.04](https://doi.org/10.21511/im.15(4).2019.04)
- 3) Bangkok Post. (2022, July 17). *Introducing Outside a New Oat Milk Born in Singapore and Made Delicious*. <https://www.bangkokpost.com/thailand/pr/2328508/introducing-outside-a-new-oat-milk-born-in-singapore-and-made-delicious>
- 4) Chen, Y. S. (2010). The drivers of green brand equity: Green brand image, green satisfaction, and green trust. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 93(2), 307–319. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-009-0223-9>
- 5) Davari, A., & Strutton, D. (2014). Marketing mix strategies for closing the gap between green consumers' pro-environmental beliefs and behaviors. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, December, 37–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0965254X.2014.914059>

- 6) El-Adly, M. I. (2019). Modelling the relationship between hotel perceived value, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 50(July 2018), 322–332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2018.07.007>
- 7) Gelderman, C. J., Schijns, J., Lambrechts, W., & Vijgen, S. (2021). Green marketing as an environmental practice : The impact on green satisfaction and green loyalty in a business-to-business context. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, January, 2061–2076. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2732>
- 8) Groening, C., Sarkis, J., & Zhu, Q. (2018). Green marketing consumer-level theory review : A compendium of applied theories and further research directions. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 172, 1848–1866. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.12.002>
- 9) Indrawati. (2015). *Metode Penelitian Manajemen dan Bisnis Kovergens Teknologi Komunikasi dan Informasi*. Refika Aditama.
- 10) Indrawati, & Putri, D. A. (2018). Analyzing Factors Influencing Continuance Intention of E-Payment Adoption Using Modified UTAUT 2 Model (A Case Study of Go-Pay from Indonesia). *2018 6th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology (ICoICT)*, 167–173.
- 11) Indrawati, Putri Yones, P. C., & Muthaiyah, S. (2022). eWOM via the TikTok application and its influence on the purchase intention of something products. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 28(2), 174–184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2022.07.007>
- 12) Indrawati, Raman, M., Wai, C. K., Ariyanti, M., Mansur, D. M., Marhaeni, G. A. M. M., Tohir, L. M., Gaffar, M. R., Has, M. N., & Yuliansyah, S. (2017). *Perilaku Konsumen Individu*. Refika Aditama.
- 13) Ipsos. (2022). *Plant-based milk consumers in the United Kingdom 2022, by milk type & age group*.
- 14) Ipsos. (2024). *Hambatan Terbesar Penerapan Produk Ramah Lingkungan di Asia Tenggara*. <https://databoks.katadata.co.id/datapublish/2024/01/05/hambatan-terbesar-penerapan-produk-ramah-lingkungan-di-asia-tenggara>
- 15) Kang, S., & Hur, W. (2011). Investigating the Antecedents of Green Brand Equity : *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.281>
- 16) Kim, D. J. (2012). An investigation of the effect of online consumer trust on expectation, satisfaction, and post-expectation. *Information Systems and E-Business Management*, 10(2), 219–240. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10257-010-0136-2>
- 17) Kim, W. H., Cho, J. L., & Kim, K. S. (2019). The relationships of wine promotion, customer satisfaction, and behavioral intention: The moderating roles of customers' gender and age. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 39(January), 212–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2019.03.001>
- 18) Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). *Marketing Management (Fifteenth)*. Pearson.
- 19) Mogaji, E., Adeola, O., Adisa, I., Hinson, R. E., Mukonza, C., & Kirgiz, A. C. (2022). *Green Marketing in Emerging Economies An Communications Perspective*. Springer Nature Switzerland AG. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-82572-0>
- 20) Mukonza, C., & Swarts, I. (2020). The influence of green marketing strategies on business performance and corporate image in the retail sector. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 29(3), 838–845. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2401>
- 21) Nguyen-viet, B. (2022). The impact of green marketing mix elements on green customer based brand equity in an emerging market. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*, 15(1), 96–116. <https://doi.org/10.1108/APJBA-08-2021-0398>
- 22) Rakuten Insight. (2023, May 2). *Share of expenditure on food and non-food among urban households in Indonesia from March 2016 to March 2022*. Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1130395/indonesia-food-and-non-food-expenditure-breakdown-urban-areas/>
- 23) Saini, N. (2022, March 1). *Outside Founder and CEO Benedict Lim on whats make local oat milk brand distinct*. Prestigeonline.Com. <https://www.prestigeonline.com/sg/people/interview-oatside-benedict-lim-singaporean-behind-local-oatmilk-brand-oatside/>
- 24) Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research Methods for Business (Seventh Ed)*. John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- 25) Statista Market Insight. (2023). *Milk Substitutes*. Statista.Com. <https://www.statista.com/outlook/cmo/food/dairy-products-eggs/milk-substitutes/indonesia>

- 26) Tripathi, A., & Pandey, N. (2018). Does impact of price endings differ for the non-green and green products?: Role of product categories and price levels. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 35(2), 143–156. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCM-06-2016-1838>
- 27) Troudi, H., & Bouyoucef, D. (2020). Predicting purchasing behavior of green food in Algerian context. *EuroMed Journal of Business*, 15(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EMJB-03-2019-0046>
- 28) Ubirajara, J., Jr, G., Reni, L., Souza, M. De, Medeiros, G., Beatriz, A., Sousa, L. De, Oly, N., Jose, C., Jabbour, C., Borchardt, M., & Zvirtes, L. (2021). Green marketing in supermarkets : Conventional and digitized marketing alternatives to reduce waste. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.12653>

Cite this Article: Fayza Najeela Pakutandang, Indrawati (2024). *The Impact of Green Marketing Mix on Green Loyalty in Outside Plant Based Milk Product with Green Satisfaction as Intervening Variable. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 7(5), 3505-3516